

D4.5. Testing, signal quality and performance enhancement of the wearable sensor network

M. Jucevicius [KTU], J. Cessana [ComTech], M. Huopainen [TAU],
S. Balling [MEDIS], S. Daukantas [KTU], R. Eitminavičius [KTU],
J. Querengaeser [MEDIS], S. Maja [TAU], R. Ahola [TAU],
A. Rapalis [KTU], S. Didaskalou [ATHENA], A. Lukoševičius [KTU],
A. Vehkaoja [TAU], V. Marozas [KTU], E. Kaldoudi [ATHENA]

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ThrombUS+ Consortium

ATHENA	Research and Innovation Center in Information, Communication and Knowledge Technologies, Greece	Eleni Kaldoudi kaldoudi@athenarc.gr
KTU	Kaunas University of Technology Lithuania	Vaidotas Marozas vaidotas.marozas@ktu.lt
VERMON	Vermon SA France	Mathieu Legros m.legros@vermon.com
FRAUNHOFER	Institute for Photonic Microsystems, Fraunhofer Germany	Nicolas Lange Nicolas.Lange@ipms.fraunhofer.de
TELEMED	Telemed Ultrasound Medical Systems Lithuania	Dmitry Novikov d.novikov@pcultrasound.com
EchoNous	EchoNous Inc USA	Pavlos Moustakidis pavlos.moustakidis@echonous.com
MEDIS	medis Medizinische Messtechnik GmbH Germany	Susann Balling sb@medis.company
ComfTech	ComfTech SLR Italy	Lara Alessia Moltani alessia.moltani@comfttech.com
TAU	Faculty of Medicine and Health Technology Tampere University, Finland	Antti Vehkaoja antti.vehkaoja@tuni.fi
LMSU	Lithuanian University of Health Science Lithuania	Andrius Macas andrius.macas@ismu.lt
GNP	Papageorgiou General Hospital Greece	Maria Bigaki pmo@papageorgiou-hospital.gr
CSS-IRCCS	Home Relief of Suffering Hospital Italy	Elvira Grandone e.grandone@operapadrepio.it
HSV	Simon Veil Hospital France	Maxime Gautier maxime.gautier@ch-simoneveil.fr
VDE	Association for Electrical, Electronic & Information Technologies, Germany	Thorsten Prinz thorsten.prinz@vde.com
MEDEA	MEDEA SRL Italy	Pietro Dionisio p.dionisio@medeaproject.eu
PHAZE	Clinical Research and Pharma Consulting SA Greece	Spiros Anagnostopoulos spiros.anagnostopoulos@phazeclinical.com
PBY	PredictBy Research and Consulting SL Spain	Frans Folkvord ffolkvord@predictby.com
SciGen	SciGen Technologies SA Greece	Katerina Pavlidi katerina.Pavlidi@scigentech.com

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Responsible Partner:	KTU
Authors:	M. Jucevicius [KTU], J. Cessana [ComTech], M. Huopalainen [TAU], S. Balling [MEDIS], S. Daukantas [KTU], R. Eitminavičius [KTU], J. Querengaeser [MEDIS], S. Maja [TAU], R. Ahola [TAU], A. Rapalis [KTU], S. Didaskalou [ATHENA], A. Lukoševičius [KTU], A. Vehkaoja [TAU], V. Marozas [KTU], E. Kaldoudi [ATHENA]
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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

Deliverable D4.5 Description

Deliverable 4.5 is a direct output of Task 4.5.

T4.5 aims to assess and **improve the signal quality, and performance** of the ThrombUS+ wearable sensor network (WSN). We will **compare the quality of the multi-sensor data to predefined patterns and test plans**. We will study the timing of tissue compression to determine when multichannel sampling should be triggered to recognize changes in a patient's vital signs. The activity sensing network data will supplement the decision-making process for suspending false alarms and identifying DVT progression, thus **improving the system's overall signal quality and performance**. KTU will lead this task as the expert on testing sensors and sensor networks. ComfTech, TAU, MEDIS, ATHENA will participate to ensure uptake of testing results and equivalent adjustments.

D4.5 is a report detailing the results of testing the ThrombUS+ wearable prototypes developed in WP4 and required quality improvements

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
ADC	Analog to Digital Converter
CHI	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Central Hub & Intelligence unit
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DFT	Discrete Fourier transform
DVT	Deep Vein Thrombosis
EIM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Electrical Impedance Module
FDM	Fused Deposition Modelling
GUI	Graphical User Interface
IR	Infrared
LAM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Limb Activity Module
LiPo	Lithium Polymer
LRM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Light Rheography Module
VOP	Venous Occlusion Plethysmography
PLA	Polylactic Acid
PPG	Photoplethysmography
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
SD	Secure Digital
SD	Secure Digital
SDK	Software Development Kit
SLA	Stereolithography
TC	Test Case
VOP	Venous Occlusion Plethysmography
WLAN	Wireless Local Area Network
WSN	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Sensors Network
WTC	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Thigh Cuff

Executive Summary

The aim of this document is to define testing protocols and procedures, as well as to describe the test results for individual modules of the wearable sensor network (WSN), in order to ensure compliance with system and user requirements. The document focuses on testing four components of the wearable sensors network (WSN): the Electrical Impedance Module (EIM), the Light Rheography Module (LRM), the Limb Activity Module (LAM), and the textile wearable used for mounting all sensors.

The hardware testing of electrical impedance module (EIM), light rheography module (LRM) and limb activity module (LAM), covering both the measurement performance and device's general functionality, showed that all devices are sufficiently accurate, perform as expected and cover all user and system requirements defined in D2.3

All test results are presented in protocol tables, which indicate which requirements are validated by specific tests. Where certain tests require more detailed explanation, this is provided below the corresponding tables. Additionally, the document includes demonstration sections for each module, aimed at showcasing the systems and their user interfaces in operation.

The functional testing of the textile wearable of the ThrombUS+ wearable sensor network showed that the design is suitable for integrating all systems developed in WP3 and WP4 effectively and ergonomically. The cleaning procedure tests of wearable showed that the prototype sustained its mechanical and electrical properties after the cleaning procedures.

This document will be updated as necessary throughout the duration of the project, incorporating relevant information, issues, and procedural changes. Each time the document is revised, all partners will be duly informed of the updates and the changes made compared to the previous version.

1. Introduction

1.1. Methodology

This deliverable presents testing, signal quality and performance enhancement of the wearable sensor network consisting of three types of sensors Electrical Impedance Module (EIM), Light Reflection Module (LRM), Light Rheography Module (LRM), and textile wearable components.

Rationale of testing methodology: System requirements are directly derived by and are linked to specific user requirements. Therefore, testing and evaluating the user requirements relies on testing protocols developed based on system requirements, which are measurable technical parameters, rather than evaluating user requirements *per se*. If all system requirements that are derived by and linked to a specific user requirement, are verified, then the user requirement itself is verified simultaneously.

Based on the abovementioned, test cases for all system requirements have been identified. For readability, system requirements were separated into technical (measurable) and function (verifiable) requirements. Each test case (TC) has a unique ID that is derived from combining the module it corresponds to and an increasing number i.e. "TC_[Module]_[Number]". The following tables that describe each test case include:

- the system requirement identifier(s),
- a short description of the test,
- the procedure, or the steps, required to implement each test case,
- the acceptance criteria required for positive outcome of the test case,
- the outcome of the test, that can be either "Pass" or "Fail" and may have short description of the results.

Finally, the user requirements verification for all modules are presented in the form of tables that include:

- the list of all user requirements of the module,
- the description of the user requirement,
- the test case ID(s) that verify the user requirement,
- the outcome of the verification, that can be "Verified", "Not verified" or N/A indicating that this specific user and the respective system requirement(s) cannot be evaluated by laboratory testing protocols and before the final integration of the various modules.
-

2. Electrical Impedance Module (EIM)

2.1. EIM description

The electrical impedance module measures body impedance in bipolar or tetrapolar configuration. Two measurement modalities are available. The discrete Fourier transform (DFT) modality allows multi-frequency measurements (up to 20 frequencies) on frequency range from 10 to 500 kHz. In contrast the MAX30009 modality allows spot frequency measurements at 25.6, 51.2, 102.4, 204.8 and 409.6 kHz. The acquired data is transferred to the controlling PC via Wi-Fi communication. The controller of the electrical impedance module is shown in Figure 1. The electrical impedance module (EIM) utilizes band-type textile electrodes to measure impedance plethysmography signal via bipolar or tetrapolar configuration. The textile band electrodes and their placement are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 1. ThrombUS+ EIM module. A) Device casing, B), device casing opened to reveal main components, C), assembled circuit board and, D), a small plug-in containing MAX30009 modality.

Figure 2. A) Textile band electrodes and B) a schematic representation of their placement on the right calf.

The primary features requiring testing are the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) and MAX30009 measurement modalities themselves, particularly their noise and their accuracy. Based on this, different testing protocols were developed for the two modalities. Moreover, additional testing protocols were developed to assess the performance of both functional and non-functional requirements of the entire module, such as the wireless connection and power management as well as tests for the software development kit (SDK). To implement and perform all these tests, a graphical user interface (GUI) was developed to fully support electrical impedance module’s functionality (see Figure 4).

2.2. System requirements testing

Test cases and the resulting outcomes, for assessing compliance to the technical system requirements of the electrical impedance module (EIM) in a laboratory environment are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Laboratory-based technical system requirements test cases for the electrical impedance module (EIM).

Testing of DFT modality: The used excitation frequency is 51 kHz, excitation current is 2.9 mA and the sample rate is 100 Hz (unless otherwise specified).					
Test Case	Requirement identifier	Description	Procedure	Pass Criteria	Outcome
TC_EIM_01	SR_PR01_EIM_05	Test of the resistance noise level.	Use of a 20 Ω resistor.	RMS noise \leq 0.1 Ω .	Pass Noise from 1000 samples, after an initial settling time of 1s: 202 $\mu\Omega_{RMS}$
TC_EIM_02	SR_PR01_EIM_04	Test of measuring range.	Use of an adjustable resistor to find the saturation limit.	Saturation limit \geq 400 Ω .	Pass Measurement stopped working after 552.6 Ω .
TC_EIM_03	SR_PR01_EIM_06	Measure the resistance accuracy.	Measure a 90.9 Ω test resistor at different spot frequencies (25, 50, 100, 200 and 500 kHz)	Measured resistance is within \pm 10% of 90.9 Ω .	Pass Measured maximum deviation: +0.07%. Mean value of 1000 samples, after an initial settling time of 1s: - 25kHz: 90.910 Ω - 50kHz: 90.910 Ω - 100kHz: 90.912 Ω - 200kHz: 90.920 Ω - 500kHz: 90.964 Ω
TC_EIM_04	SR_PR01_EIM_03	Measure the excitation current.	Measure the excitation voltage (and thus current) across a 90.9 Ω test resistor with an oscilloscope. Test is performed at 200 kHz.	Measure peak-to-peak amplitude is 530 mV \pm 10%.	Pass Amplitude is within 530 mV \pm 10%. According to oscilloscope's own peak-to-peak measurement: 538 mVpp.
Testing of MAX30009 modality: The used excitation frequency is 51.2 kHz, excitation current is 1.28 mA and sample rate is 100 Hz (unless otherwise specified).					
Test Case	Requirement identifier	Description	Procedure	Pass Criteria	Outcome
TC_EIM_05	SR_PR01_EIM_05	Test of the resistance noise level	Use of a 20 Ω resistor.	RMS noise \leq 0.1 Ω	Pass Noise from 1000 samples, after an initial settling time of 5s: 688 $\mu\Omega_{RMS}$.

TC_EIM_06	SR_PR01_EIM_04	Test of measuring range.	Use of an adjustable resistor to find the saturation limit at 32, 64, 128, 256, 640 and 1280 μ A measurement currents.	Saturation limit must be $\geq 400 \Omega$, at least on one range.	Pass Saturation limit is over 400Ω at 256μ A and lower ranges. Measurement stopped working at: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1280μA: 96.407Ω - 640μA: 183.304Ω - 256μA: 455.628Ω - 128μA: 906.766Ω - 64μA: $>1022 \Omega$ - 32μA: $>1022 \Omega$ (1022Ω : setup's upper limit)
TC_EIM_07	SR_PR01_EIM_06	Measure the resistance accuracy.	Measure a 20Ω test resistor at 51.2 kHz .	Measured resistance is within $\pm 10\%$ of 20Ω .	Pass Measured resistance is within $\pm 10\%$ of 20Ω . Mean value of 1000 samples, after an initial settling time of 5s: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 51.2 kHz: 20.957Ω. - Short circuit at 51.2 kHz: 0.028Ω.
Other technical requirements tests					
Test Case	Requirement identifier	Description	Procedure	Pass Criteria	Outcome
TC_EIM_08	SR_PR01_EIM_08	Testing of measurement time.	Charge device for at least 8 hours. Use a multimeter to measure device's current drain directly from battery terminals: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) when the device is off, b) when the device is idle but connected to a Wi-Fi access point and, c) when measurement is running. 	The measured currents are below: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) 1 mA, b) 200 mA, c) 500 mA. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Pass Off current is less than 1 mA. b) Pass Idle current is less than 200 mA. c) Pass Measurement current is less than 500 mA. Current measurements using Fluke 87V's μ A range for off-state and ampere range for the others. Device off: 1.2μ A. Device Idle: $100 \dots 120 \text{ mA}$. Measuring: 280 to 350 mA (considerable fluctuation)
TC_EIM_09	SR_PR01_EIM_01	Test of bipolar measurement.	A 20Ω test resistor is connected as	a) Bipolar mode	a) Pass Bipolar mode's

			required for bipolar measurement. Impedance is measured (DFT, 51 kHz, 2.9 mA) first in bipolar mode and then in tetrapolar mode.	produces valid impedance readings (20 ohms, $\pm 5\%$) b) Tetrapolar measurement does not start.	resistance readings are within 5% of 20 Ω . b) Pass Tetrapolar measurement does not start. Measured resistance in bipolar mode (average of 1000 samples, after 1s settling): 20.098 Ω Measured resistance in tetrapolar mode: measurement does not start, reported error code ERR_MEASERROR.
TC_EIM_10	SR_PR01_EIM_01	Testing of tetrapolar measurement.	A 20 Ω test resistor is connected as required for tetrapolar measurement. Impedance is measured (DFT, 51 kHz, 2.9 mA) first in bipolar mode and then in tetrapolar mode.	Both modes produce valid impedance readings (20 ohms, $\pm 5\%$)	Pass The readings in both modes are within 5% of 20 Ω . Average resistance in bipolar mode of 1000 samples after 1s settling: 20.099 Ω . Average resistance in tetrapolar mode of 1000 samples after 1s settling: 20.009 Ω .
TC_EIM_11	SR_PR01_EIM_16	Testing of sampling rate.	A 20 Ω test resistor is connected and a measurement is started using the default configuration (DFT, 4 leads, 1.28 mA current, 100 Hz sample rate). Measurement is left to run for 20 minutes ± 5 seconds. Data is saved to a file.	The output file must contain 120000 samples (= 20 minutes worth), $\pm 1\%$.	Pass The collected number of samples is within 1% of the expected amount. 20 minutes of data was collected at 100Hz data rate; manual start/stop was presumably accurate within 2 seconds. Samples collected: 119973, resulting in a deviation of -0.02% off from nominal 120000.

TC_EIM_04. Unlike most tests, where the results were extracted directly from the data files produced by the instrument, test TC_EIM_04 was performed with an oscilloscope and the amplitude was determined by the oscilloscope's own peak-to-peak amplitude calculator. As this calculator can be inaccurate with noisy signals, the amplitude was also determined manually from the screen capture shown in Figure 3. The manually determined result is about 510mV_{pp}, which is still well within the limits (530mV_{pp} $\pm 10\%$).

Figure 3. Oscilloscope screenshot of test TC_EIM_04: voltage across a 90.9 Ω test resistor, caused by 200 kHz excitation current.

Table 2. Laboratory-based functional system requirements test cases for the electrical impedance module (EIM).

Test Case	Requirement identifier	Description	Procedure	Pass Criteria	Outcome
General functionality testing					
TC_EIM_12	SR_PRO1_EIM_07	Testing of Wi-Fi connectivity.	PC software is used to connect to the device.	PC software can connect to the device.	Pass PC software can connect to the device. Test performed as part of the earlier technical tests, requiring Wi-Fi connection to the device.
TC_EIM_13	SR_PRO1_EIM_08	Testing of charging.	Device is powered on for at least 8 hours. After that, the device is powered off and connected to a USB charger for at least 24 hours. PC software is used to query the battery voltage before and after charging.	Voltage after charging is over 4 volts and at least 50 mV higher than before it.	Pass Voltage after charging is over 4V and more than 50mV higher than before charging. Initial voltage after keeping the device in idle mode for 9 hours: 3.8177V. After 24 hours of charging: 4.1421V.
Testing of software development kit (SDK).					
TC_EIM_14	SR_PRO1_EIM_14	Testing of device's default settings.	Start and connect the device to the software.	Initial device settings displayed in the GUI are [DFT / 4 leads / 100 Hz/ 1280 µA /	Pass

				51 kHz / 0 (Single)].	
TC_EIM_15	SR_PR01_EIM_14	Start measurement	Start measurement by clicking on GUI button using the device's default settings.	Waveform data starts rendering; Editing device settings is disabled.	Pass
TC_EIM_16	SR_PR01_EIM_14	Stop measurement	Stop measurement by clicking on GUI button.	Waveform data in GUI stops updating; Editing device settings is enabled.	Pass
TC_EIM_17	SR_PR01_EIM_14	Adjust settings	In GUI, set device settings to [MAX30009, 2 leads, 50 Hz, 640 μ A, 25.6 kHz].	Settings displayed in the GUI match the requested settings.	Pass
TC_EIM_18	SR_PR01_EIM_14	Multi-frequency measurement	In GUI, set device settings to [DFT, 4 leads, 100 Hz, 1280 μ A, 51 and 71 kHz].	Settings displayed in the GUI match the requested settings.	Pass
TC_EIM_19	SR_PR01_EIM_17	Connection status	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Power on the device and wait 15 seconds. 2. Power down the device. 3. Repeat 3 times. 	Device connection status in the GUI updates to match device state within 10 seconds of state change.	Pass
TC_EIM_20	SR_PR01_EIM_17	Current device mode	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Connect device 2. Switch between settings and measurement modes. 	Device mode status updates properly.	Pass
TC_EIM_21	SR_PR01_EIM_17	Battery status	Connect device.	Device battery level (0–100 %) is displayed in the GUI.	Pass
TC_EIM_22	SR_PR01_EIM_17	Low battery status	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Connect device with a battery voltage under 3.44V. 2. Start measurement. 	A “Low battery” status message is displayed in the GUI.	Pass
TC_EIM_23	SR_PR01_EIM_17	Leads off status	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Connect device. 2. Start measurement. 3. Detach a wire from the device. 	A “Leads off” status message is displayed in the GUI.	Pass

TC_EIM_24	SR_PR01_EIM_07	IPG Signal rendering	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Connect device. 2. Connect device to decade resistance box, set 2 lead mode. 3. Start measurement. 4. Use range of 10-50 ohm. 5. Record measurement for 15 seconds. 6. Take screen capture of rendered waveforms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IPG waveform is properly rendered in the GUI. - Waveforms in the screen capture image match those recorded in the data. 	Pass
TC_EIM_25	SR_PR01_EIM_07	EIP-extracted parameters	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Connect device to a synthetic data source. 2. Complete a VOP measurement. 	<p>Extracted parameters are displayed in the GUI after the VOP measurement is completed:</p> <p>Venous capacity, venous outflow.</p>	Pass
TC_EIM_26	SR_PR01_EIM_17	Event logging	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Connect device. 2. Change device settings to differ from the default settings. 3. Start measurement. 4. Stop measurement after 30 seconds. 	<p>System events (device connection/disconnection, setting changes, measurement start/stop, file writes) are logged in event.log file.</p>	Pass
TC_EIM_27	SR_PR01_EIM_17	Error logging	<p>Using an error-producing synthetic data source and adding error-inducing code to the SDK, cause:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. device disconnection during measurement, 2. file write failure, 3. clipping/buffering measurement status flags, 4. device-initiated measurement stops. 	<p>System errors are logged in error.log file.</p>	Pass

2.3. User requirements verification

Based on the above-mentioned test cases and the resulting outcomes, the verification of the identified user requirements for the electrical impedance module is performed by the same System requirements test cases, that stem from the User requirements. All user requirements for the electrical impedance module (EIM) are listed below in Table 3, with listed corresponding test cases that verify each user requirement.

Table 3.Verification of electrical impedance module (EIM) user requirements based on laboratory testing.

User Requirement	User Requirement Description	Test Case ID(s)	Outcome
UR_PR01_EIM_01_02	To provide sufficient bioimpedance signal quality and resolution to discriminate physiological from pathological condition	TC_EIM_01 TC_EIM_02 TC_EIM_03 TC_EIM_05 TC_EIM_06 TC_EIM_07 TC_EIM_11	Verified
UR_PR01_EIM_02_01	To support automatic calibration of EIM module	TC_EIM_03 TC_EIM_07	Verified
UR_PR01_EIM_03_01	To be biocompatible ensuring no adverse reaction during prolonged wear	TC_WSN_13	Not verified yet
UR_PR01_EIM_04_01	Electrodes should have a reliable contact with the skin and be reusable.	TC_WSN_14	Verified
UR_PR01_EIM_05_01	To permit easy wearing procedure	TC_WSN_15	Verified
UR_PR01_EIM_06_01	To be wireless - work on battery and have wireless communication	TC_EIM_08 TC_EIM_12 TC_EIM_14 TC_EIM_27	Verified

2.4. Signal quality and performance demonstration

The developed experimental graphical user interface (GUI) is based on the electrical impedance module's (EIM) software development kit (SDK) and fully supports electrical impedance module's functionality accessible through the SDK. It allows performing tests related to device settings and control commands, as well as to provide the ability to change measurement device settings, start and stop a measurement and estimate signal quality. Figure 4 presents a screen capture of the experimental graphical user interface (GUI) displaying a venous occlusion plethysmography (VOP) testing signal.

As seen in the graphical user interface (GUI), the signals are of sufficient quality to assess bioimpedance changes in tissue, that happen due to venous blood flow

The electrical impedance module (EIM) hardware testing, covering both the measurement performance and device's general functionality, showed that the device is sufficiently accurate, performs as expected and covers all user and system requirements. The developed technical graphical user interface (GUI) allowed the testing and demonstration of the system operation and will facilitate integration in the project scope. Functional tests related to the electrical impedance module (EIM) software development kit (SDK) demonstrated that the developed SDK provides the required functionality to control the measurement device. Therefore, the system is suitable for measuring bioimpedance from lower limbs.

Figure 4. EIM Technical GUI displays a VOP testing signal.

3. Light Rheography Module (LRM)

3.1. LRM description

Capitalizing on MEDIS' extensive expertise in non-invasive cardiovascular diagnostic techniques, such as light reflection rheography, the subsequent advancement of the light reflection rheography (LRR) method from a desktop device to a wearable one was initiated. The objective of the work package was to assure the fulfilment of the technical and user requirements for a wireless sensor with battery supply and embedded microcontroller.

A detailed description of the work package can be found in Deliverable 4.2¹. Since then, the concepts of battery management and hardware dimensioning have been further developed, and a prototype containing a case has been created.

Following the validation of the hardware prototype's functionality, including its capacity to traverse the chosen textiles and achieve the expected level of accuracy in data acquisition, the subsequent design of the appropriate case could be initiated. An illustration of the LRR sensor hardware is provided in Figure 5.

The prototype design depicted in the Figure 5 has a size of 10 mm by 42 mm. Consequently, the dimensions of the device are comparable to those of modern smart watches. The lightweight realization of 12 g ensures convenient integration into the intended textile wearable system.

The battery supply, in the form of a lithium polymer (LiPo) accumulator with a capacity of 200 mAh, was appropriately sized to support the necessary power demands of the system. The intelligent processing component was enabled by the integration of an embedded microcontroller, designated as the ESP32 S3. Additionally, the system featured wireless local area network (WLAN) data communication, allowing for the transmission of data from the wireless network directly to the central hub and intelligence unit (CHI) without the need for physical connections or additional hardware components. However, the claims for a small device and relatively high power consumption necessitated certain compromises in the hardware and software design. Consequently, a deep sleep mode was implemented to reduce power consumption during periods of inactivity. Prior to utilization, the device has to be manually activated. The wireless local area network

¹ Balling S, Querengässer J, Schubert F, Sensors and processing software for light reflection rheography DVT detection, Deliverable 4.2, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 05 January 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14540537>.

(WLAN) connection is initiated by the user's request to start a measurement. Furthermore, the frequency of the ESP32 has been reduced to 80 MHz.

The functional prototype has been integrated effectively into the textile design, as illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Finished printed circuit board in a compact design.

Figure 6. Embedding of the prototype in the textile.

3.2. System requirements testing

Test cases and the resulting outcomes, for assessing compliance with the technical system requirements of the electrical impedance module (EIM) in a laboratory environment are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Laboratory-based technical system requirements test cases for the Light Rheography Module (LRM).

Test Case	Requirement identifier	Description	Procedure	Pass Criteria	Outcome
TC_LRM_01	SR_PRO1_LRM_02	Infrared light with a wavelength of 950 nm	Manufacturer information in the data sheet	LRM sensor wavelength = 950 nm (see datasheet of LED)	Pass
TC_LRM_02	SR_PRO1_LRM_13	Status display RGB LED	LED state depends on device mode	see Software requirements	Pass
TC_LRM_03	SR_PRO1_LRM_12	Automatic sensor adjustment	Measurements on skin and through textile of prototype	Similar curve shape between measurements (skin <--> textile)	Pass

TC_LRM_04	SR_PR01_LRM_01	Sampling rate of 10 Hz	Checking time stamp of UDP messages	60 samples per minute received	Pass
TC_LRM_05	SR_PR01_LRM_04	Biocompatibility	The Case is biocompatible.	Passed safety test: A biological certificate is available that proves conformity in accordance with DIN EN ISO 10993-5.	Pass
TC_LRM_06	SR_PR01_LRM_06	Compliance and Safety	Complies with relevant medical standards, IEC 60601, for electrical medical devices and must be designed to prevent interference with other medical equipment and ensure it operates in noisy environments without degradation in performance.	Pass IEC 60601 and performance testing	Pass
TC_LRM_07	SR_PR01_LRM_09	Wi-Fi connectivity	PC software is used to connect to the device.	PC software can connect to the device.	Pass
TC_LRM_08	SR_PR01_LRM_05 SR_PR01_LRM_10	Device button	Button is pressed shortly to awaken the device from deep sleep	Device enters standby mode (status LED flashes)	Pass
TC_LRM_09	SR_PR01_LRM_05	Charging	Device is connected to magnetic connector. Charging process can be observed by status UDP messages.	Voltage must raise until 4.2 V. Charging is terminated by hardware. This is indicated by status UDP messages.	Pass
TC_LRM_10	SR_PR01_LRM_10	Power Supply	The sensor can take several measurements and does not need to be recharged after each measurement.	Passed performance and safety tests: LRR sensors measures over a cycle of 10 measurements. Longer power supply in deep sleep is possible.	Pass
TC_LRM_11	SR_PR01_LRM_07	Data processing	The LRR data processing is performed in the LRR sensor.	Passed performance tests: The values are calculated within the LRR sensor. The final measured values and calculated parameters can be transferred directly to CHI.	Pass
TC_LRM_12	SR_PR01_LRM_11	Attachment	LRM modules must be attachable to lower extremity segments using comfortable Velcro straps.	Fixation with velcro straps possible.	Pass

The commissioning of the first four completed prototypes included a technical check to verify the analogue performance of the hardware as part of TC_LRM_06. The details are provided in Table 5, while the testing graphs of the last row are presented enlarged in Figures 7-10.

Table 5. Technical validation during prototype production.

Prototype	LRM_F03088	LRM_F03080	LRM_F030AC	LRM_F030B4
Measurement points: 3.3 V	+3.29 V	3.33 V	3.30 V	3.29 V
Voltage transformation:	+4.99 V	+4.85 V	+5.06 V	+5.01 V
Supply voltages: V+	+4.99 V	+5.05 V	+5.06 V	+5.01 V
Supply voltages: V-	-4.81 V	-4.85 V	-4.86 V	-4.81 V
Testing graph:				

Technical testing of prototype LRM_F03088

Figure 7. Testing of prototype LRM_F03088.

Technical testing of prototype LRM_F03080

Figure 8. Testing of prototype LRM_F03080.

Technical testing of prototype LRM_F030AC

Figure 9. Testing of prototype LRM_F030AC.

Figure 10. Testing of prototype LRM_F030B4.

The test case TC_LRM_06, in particular, was verified with the corresponding course of the LRM hardware curves.

3.3. User requirements verification

Based on the above-mentioned test cases and the resulting outcomes, the verification of the identified user requirements for the electrical impedance module is performed by the same System requirements test cases, that stem from the User requirements. All user requirements for the light rheography module (LRM) are listed below in Table 6, with listed corresponding test cases that verify each user requirement.

Table 6. Verification of light rheography module user requirements based on laboratory testing.

User Requirement	User Requirement Description	Test Case ID(s)	Outcome
UR_PR01_LRM_01_01	To provide sufficient light rheography signal quality and resolution to discriminate physiological from pathological condition	TC_LRM_03	Verified
UR_PR01_LRM_02_01	Sensors should be reusable	TC_LRM_08 TC_LRM_09	Verified
UR_PR01_LRM_03_02	To be biocompatible ensuring no adverse reaction during prolonged wear	TC_LRM_05	Verified
UR_PR01_LRM_04_02	A central display of the data is made available via the CHI. The CHI does not need to perform any further algorithmic calculations as this is done within the sensor.	TC_LRM_11	Verified
UR_PR01_LRM_05_02	A central display of the data is made available via the CHI. The user does not need any additional UI.	TC_LRM_08 TC_LRM_11	Verified
UR_PR01_LRM_06_01	To be wireless - work on battery and have wireless communication	TC_LRM_07 TC_LRM_09	Verified
UR_PR01_LRM_07_01	The sensor can take several measurements and does not need to be recharged after each measurement.	TC_LRM_10	Verified
UR_PR01_LRM_08_02	To permit easy wearing procedure	TC_LRM_03 TC_LRM_12	Verified
UR_PR01_LRM_09_02	There is no electrical risk to the user.	TC_LRM_06	Verified

UR_PR01_LRM_10_02	The integrated battery is intended to be charged. There are no obstructions due to cables.	TC_LRM_09	Verified
UR_PR01_LRM_11_02	It is possible to measure different skin types and through textiles.	TC_LRM_03	Verified
UR_PR01_LRM_12_02	The user is informed about the status of the sensor (e.g. connectivity).	TC_LRM_02	Verified

3.4. Signal quality and performance demonstration

As evidenced by the Figure 11, the objective of the testing procedure was to evaluate the signal quality and performance of the developed prototype. Accordingly, the prototype was attached to the inside of the right lower leg of a healthy test subject, in accordance with the intended position for LRR measurement. The case was secured by a flexible band. The test subject assumed a seated position with both feet placed parallel on the floor.

After the initiation of the LRR test measurement and the automated sensor calibration in the preliminary phase, the test subject commenced the dorsiflexions. Subsequent to the tenth repetition, he returned to the initial position, characterized by feet parallel on the floor, and maintained this posture without further movement. The resulting refill phase was recorded.

The curve provides a visual representation of the phase of the muscle pump test and the subsequent refilling. The process follows the expected pattern. Therefore, the sensor fulfils the requirements regarding signal quality and performance.

Figure 11. Signal quality and performance demonstration of LRM sensor: x-axis – time (samples), y-axis – volume (samples).

4. Limb Activity Module (LAM)

4.1. LAM description

Two iterations of the limb activity module (LAM) were developed. The second iteration of the module includes a wireless, battery powered control and data transmission device, and for each leg – a cable with possibility to connect 5 sensors, that can be integrated into a textile wearable of the ThrombUS+ wearable sensor network. Each sensor node includes activity and orientation, as well as temperature and photoplethysmography (PPG) sensors. The sensors were designed to be easily and firmly integrated to the textile wearable and manufactured from biocompatible resin by stereolithography (SLA) 3D print technology. The sensor design and manufactured assembly with electronics are shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. The sensor design and already manufactured assembly with electronics.

The control and data transmission device design is presented in Figure 13. It has a removable Li-ion battery, separate connectors for sensor chain of each leg, a display and an SD card for additionally logging all data. The body was manufactured from PLA by fused deposition modelling (FDM) 3D printing technology.

Figure 13. 3D Design for the housing of the main control and data collection device.

A working assembly of the limb activity module (LAM) system is presented in Figure 14.

Figure 14. A working assembly of the second LAM iteration.

Software development kit (SDK) for limb activity module (LAM) control and data collection was built and software development kit -based experimental graphical user interface (GUI) utilizing all software development kit (SDK) functionality was developed for testing and demonstration of the limb activity module (LAM). System and SDK functionalities include updating system settings by one button, which include selecting active sensors, active signals, sampling rate and transmission rate (window). The SDK has implemented self-adjusting data package size, and has functions for calibration, zero orientation setting as well as starting and stopping of the measurement. The developed experimental graphical user interface (GUI) allows to use all software development kit (SDK) functionality and visualize data for a total of 6 sensors, 3 for each leg. The system and the software development kit (SDK) are capable operating a total of 10 sensors.

4.2. System requirements testing

Test cases and the resulting outcomes, for assessing compliance with the technical system requirements of the limb activity module (LAM) in a laboratory environment are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Laboratory-based technical system requirements test cases for the LAM.

Test Case	Requirement identifier	Description	Procedure	Pass Criteria	Outcome
Orientation estimation tests					
TC_LAM_01	SR_PR01_LAM_03	Static accuracy	Place LAM sensor in known static orientations (0°, 45°, 90°, etc.) on all 3 axes	RMSE $\leq \pm 5^\circ$ across all axes	Pass RMSE during static testing was 0.34 °

TC_LAM_02	SR_PR01_LAM_03	Dynamic accuracy	Mount reference sensor to LAM sensor. Perform moderate activity for 1 minute.	RMSE $\leq \pm 5^\circ$ when compared to reference system TrakStar (NDI, Canada)	Pass RMSE during dynamic testing was 3.5°
Temperature measurement tests					
TC_LAM_03	SR_PR01_LAM_13 SR_PR01_LAM_14	Ambient temperature measurement evaluation	Place in controlled temperatures (e.g., 20, 25, 30 °C)	± 0.2 °C deviation from reference	Pass Temperature deviation 0.17 °C from reference
TC_LAM_04	SR_PR01_LAM_13 SR_PR01_LAM_14	Body temperature measurement evaluation	Measure reference temperature; Place on body.	± 0.2 °C deviation from reference	Pass. Temperature deviation 0.14 °C from reference
PPG recording tests					
TC_LAM_05	SR_PR01_LAM_15	Four channel PPG evaluation	Collect and review PPG data in four available channels	PPG signals in all four channels has signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) not lower than 20dB.	Pass Average SNR of all signals was 23.2 dB
Data rate and sampling control tests					
TC_LAM_06	SR_PR01_LAM_02	Configurable rates	Change sampling rate to 1, 10, 25, 50 Hz via SDK	Actual rate matches config ± 1 sps	Pass
TC_LAM_07	SR_PR01_LAM_03	Full multi-sensor rate test	Enable all sensors, run at 50 Hz	System remains stable, no dropped packets	Pass
Test Case	Requirement identifier	Description	Procedure	Pass Criteria	Outcome
Other technical tests					
TC_LAM_08	SR_PR01_LAM_08	The LAM communicates with the CHI via Wi-Fi	Connect and operate the device	Communication with device via Wifi successful. Device received commands, CHI receives device status and data.	Pass
TC_LAM_09	SR_PR01_LAM_09	LAM uses a rechargeable battery for at least 1 day of intermittent monitoring	Device left for 24 hours with signal registration and transmission ON	The device battery did not run out in 24 hours.	Pass

TC_LAM_10	SR_PR01_LAM_10	The LAM can be disinfected and complies with the safety indices on potential thermal and mechanical hazards as described in the IEC 60601-1 standard.	LAM system is disinfected by rubbing with 90% ethanol. The system is turned on operated in normal conditions.	The system did not show any signs of chemical and mechanical damage from cleaning. The operation of the system is unchanged.	Pass
TC_LAM_11	SR_PR01_LAM_11	The LAM provides an SDK for data processing and programming interfaces.	The system is operated using technical GUI based on provided SDK	The system responds to configuration changes and is performing all stated functions.	Pass
TC_LAM_12	SR_PR01_LAM_12	System is designed in a way to be firmly integrated into ThrombUS+ wearable	Insert system in the wearable	Sensor operation and ergonomics of the textile wearable is unchanged.	Pass
TC_LAM_13	SR_PR01_LAM_17	Device has a replaceable battery that is easy to mount and remove.	Confirming removable battery; Evaluating battery mounting mechanism.	Battery can be removed and mounted without excessive force and complex locks.	Pass
TC_LAM_14	SR_PR01_LAM_18	System has a screen for viewing its status	Evaluating if screen readable and shows necessary status information	Screen shows battery level, and status (boot, ready, measuring, error)	Pass
TC_LAM_15	SR_PR01_LAM_18	System has automatic calibration and orientation reset functions	Performing calibration and orientation reset	Raw gyroscope data is near zero and orientation not changing after calibration; Quaternion orientation is (1,0,0,0) after orientation reset.	Pass

TC_LAM_01 test was performed to assess static accuracy of the LAM system. Using a fixed-in-place angle ruler and an attached reference sensor for orientation measurement TrakStar (NDI, Canada). The angle change of system orientation output was estimated at different angles of orientation, in 90° degree steps, resulting in average RMSE = 0.34° degrees.

Figure 15. TC_LAM_01 test for LAM static accuracy.

TC_LAM_02 test was performed by mounting reference sensor of a state-of-the-art position estimation system to LAM sensor, performing moderate activity for 1 minute and calculating RMSE between orientation estimates from both systems. The test resulted in RMSE = 3.5° degrees.

TC_LAM_03 test was performed by measuring temperature of a controlled heating oven at 20°, 30° and 40° degrees, along with reference temperature probe measurement by multimeter UT71B (UNIT-T, China) resulting in 0.17 °C average error for ambient temperature.

TC_LAM_04 test was performed by measuring body temperature of 5 volunteers, along with reference temperature measurement by multimeter probe UT71B (UNIT-T, China) resulting in 0.14 °C average error for body temperature.

TC_LAM_05 test was performed by recording PPG on a calf of a volunteer and assessing Signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). System requirement related to PPG signal quality requires SNR higher than 20dB, which means the signal amplitude is at least 10 times higher than the noise amplitude. The recorded signal of infrared (IR), red, green and blue light are presented in Figure 16-Figure 19 respectively. Amplitude is shown in least significant bits of analog-to-digital converter (ADC), otherwise known as ADC counts.

Figure 16. Infrared light signal from calf of a volunteer during TC_LAM_05 test, with noise visible. The SNR calculated from IR PPG signal was 20.82 dB.

Figure 17. Red light signal from calf of a volunteer during TC_LAM_05 test, with noise visible. The SNR calculated from IR PPG signal was 21.58 dB.

Figure 18. Green light signal from calf of a volunteer during TC_LAM_05 test, with noise visible. The SNR calculated from IR PPG signal was 23.52 dB.

Figure 19. Blue light signal from calf of a volunteer during TC_LAM_05 test, with noise visible. The SNR calculated from IR PPG signal was 26.02 dB.

To sum up, IR signal SNR was 20.82 dB, red signal SNR was 21.58 dB, green signal SNR was 23.52 dB and blue signal SNR was 26.02 dB. The average SNR was 23.2 dB.

Functional requirements testing protocol and results are presented below in the Table 8.

Table 8. Laboratory-based technical system requirements test cases for the Limb Activity Module (LAM).

Test Case	Requirement identifier	Description	Procedure	Pass Criteria	Outcome
System configurability					
TC_LAM_16	SR_PR01_LAM_08 SR_PR01_LAM_11	Default configuration	Power-on and read current configuration	Matches default settings (50 Hz, orientation on, raw data off, SD recording on, etc.)	Pass
TC_LAM_17	SR_PR01_LAM_07 SR_PR01_LAM_11 SR_PR01_LAM_14 SR_PR01_LAM_15	Enable/disable settings	Toggle features one by one: raw data, temp, PPG, SD recording	Features correctly enabled/disabled	Pass
TC_LAM_18	SR_PR01_LAM_19	Save & restore	Change settings, reboot system	Settings persist across restarts (or correctly reset if not persistent)	Pass
Controller display parameters tests					
TC_LAM_19	SR_PR01_LAM_18	State change	Observe display while switching system states (boot, ready, measuring, error)	Display reflects correct state in real-time	Pass

TC_LAM_20	SR_PR01_LAM_18 SR_PR01_LAM_19	Error code handling	Trigger sensor fault; observe error message/code on screen	Correct error number & label displayed	Pass
TC_LAM_21	SR_PR01_LAM_18 SR_PR01_LAM_19	Battery monitoring	Simulate battery charge/drain; observe display	Correct % level and charging status shown	Pass
SD card recording tests					
TC_LAM_22	SR_PR01_LAM_16	Recording verification	Enable SD logging, run measurements, extract data	Data matches streamed content, file format is good	Pass
TC_LAM_23	SR_PR01_LAM_16 SR_PR01_LAM_18	Card insertion/removal	Insert/remove card during operation	System handles gracefully or emits a warning	Pass
Communication via UDP and SDK					
TC_LAM_24	SR_PR01_LAM_03	Sensor data integrity	Compare received sensor data with local logs or SD card	No corruption or misalignment	Pass
TC_LAM_25	SR_PR01_LAM_08 SR_PR01_LAM_19	Heartbeat mechanism	Block packets temporarily; observe reversion to discovery	Discovery mode is entered correctly after timeout	Pass
TC_LAM_26	SR_PR01_LAM_03	Time synchronization	Verify timestamps in packets vs. system clock	Drift ≤ 10 ms over 1 min (define depending on system tolerance)	Pass
System robustness and edge cases tests					
TC_LAM_27	SR_PR01_LAM_19	Low battery	Run device until battery drains; observe behaviour	Warning issued, safe shutdown	Pass
TC_LAM_28	SR_PR01_LAM_18 SR_PR01_LAM_19	Sensor fault	Simulate IMU or temp sensor failure	Error displayed and transmitted	Pass
TC_LAM_29	SR_PR01_LAM_08 SR_PR01_LAM_19	Wi-Fi dropout	Disconnect network briefly, then reconnect	System resumes streaming or enters discovery as expected	Pass
TC_LAM_30	SR_PR01_LAM_18 SR_PR01_LAM_19	Startup without SD card	Boot without SD inserted	Logs warning but continues operating normally	Pass

4.3. User requirements verification

Based on the above-mentioned test cases and the resulting outcomes, the verification of the identified user requirements for the electrical impedance module is performed by the same system requirements test cases, that stem from the user requirements. All user requirements for the limb activity module are listed below in Table 9, with listed corresponding test cases that verify each user requirement.

Table 9. Verification of limb activity module user requirements based on laboratory testing.

User Requirement ID	User Requirement Description	Test ID's	Case	Outcome
UR_PR01_LAM_01_02	To provide sufficient real-time position and orientation signal quality for estimating orientation and monitoring the activity of each lower limb segment	TC_LAM_01 TC_LAM_02		Verified
UR_PR01_LAM_02_01	Sensors should be reusable	TC_LAM_10 TC_LAM_12		Verified
UR_PR01_LAM_03_01	To be biocompatible and ensuring no adverse reaction during prolonged wear	TC_LAM_10		Verified
UR_PR01_LAM_04_01	To permit easy wearing procedure	TC_LAM_12		Verified
UR_PR01_LAM_05_01	To support automatic calibration of LAM module	TC_LAM_15		Verified
UR_PR01_LAM_06_01	To be wireless - work on battery and have wireless communication	TC_LAM_08 TC_LAM_09		Verified
UR_PR01_LAM_07_01	To provide sufficient quality patient body and ambient temperature measurements	TC_LAM_03 TC_LAM_04		Verified
UR_PR01_LAM_08_01	To provide sufficient quality PPG measurement for vital signs monitoring and scientific research	TC_LAM_05		Verified
UR_PR01_LAM_09_01	Sensor should have a reliable optical contact with the skin and mechanical stability.	TC_LAM_12		Verified
UR_PR01_LAM_10_01	System should record all signals into memory storage media	TC_LAM_22 TC_LAM_23		Verified
UR_PR01_LAM_11_01	System should have a screen for viewing its status.	TC_LAM_14		Verified

4.4. Signal quality and performance demonstration

To control the system and perform all tests, an experimental graphical user interface (GUI) based on the limb activity module (LAM) software development kit (SDK) was developed and used. The user interface includes all limb activity module and software development kit functionalities, as well as the ability to modify all settings. The interface is shown in Figure 20.

A few experiments were conducted to test the synchronous acquisition of accelerometer and PPG signals. Figure 21 below shows a multiwavelength PPG signal synchronized with the accelerometer channel from the IMU during a dorsiflexion test (foot movement), which is commonly used in venous valve characterization through LRR analysis. The test was performed in a sitting position.

The first minute shows very low-amplitude PPG signals reflecting cardiac activity, along with a downward slope caused by accumulating venous blood in the calf. In the middle of the graph, foot movements are visible. The PPG signals corresponding to the infrared (IR) and red (R) wavelengths differ significantly from those of the green (G) and blue (B) wavelengths. This is due to the different penetration depths of light: IR and R wavelengths can reach deeper tissue layers, while green and blue light are limited to the superficial capillary layers.

The accelerometer data allow assessment of the variability in foot movement. Excessive variability could significantly degrade the results of the LRR test.

Figure 20. LAM SDK based technical GUI developed for testing and demonstration of LAM module.

Figure 21. PPG and accelerometer signals recorded by the LAM module during the foot dorsiflexion experiment.

The second experiment involved a subject with the sensor attached to the calf while lying in a horizontal position. The subject raised her leg and then returned it to the horizontal position again (Figure 22). Raising the leg causes the accumulated venous blood to flow quickly out of the calf, leading to changes in the photoplethysmography (PPG) and light reflection rheography (LRR) signals. Again, different signal behavior was observed for different wavelengths: the trend components of the infrared (IR) and red (R) signals decreased, while those of the green (G) and blue (B) signals increased. This is consistent with the expected effect of reduced blood volume and, consequently, reduced light absorption.

The protocol can be clearly observed from the synchronous accelerometer signals, which reflect orientation changes due to the sensitivity of the sensor to the Earth's gravity vector.

Figure 22. PPG and accelerometer signals recorded by the LAM module during the leg-raising experiment.

5. Textile wearable

5.1. Textile wearable description

The wearable sensor network (WSN) is composed of the wearable parts related to the previously described modules. It includes two semi-independent straps for electrical impedance module (EIM) to be used with the wearable thigh cuff (WTC), for implementing the venous occlusion plethysmography (VOP), three straps to locate the sensors (thigh, calf and foot) of the limb activity module and a sensor pocket for the light rheography sensor, to be placed on the calf strap of the limb activity module (Figure 23).

Figure 23. On the left: Schematic representation of WSN (textiles straps in black, LAM sensors in yellow, EIM electrodes in red, LRM sensor in green). On the right: WSN prototype.

The components of WSN can be combined in different ThrombUS+ system configurations, according to the different deep vein thrombosis (DVT) monitoring and prevention methods.

5.2. System requirements testing

The wearable sensor network (WSN) prototype is evaluated based on system requirements, that stem from the user requirements. Requirements can be:

- Met by design.
- Tested on volunteer and/or phantom.
- Tested with specific procedures.

If specific testing procedures are needed and can be performed by ThrombUS+ partners, the protocols and results are detailed in Section 5.4.

Technical requirements defined for electrical impedance module (EIM) related to wearable sensor network (WSN) are listed below in Table 10.

Table 10. Laboratory-based technical system requirements test cases for the textile wearable, that are related to the Electric impedance Module (EIM) requirements.

Test Case	Unique Requirement identifier	Description	Procedure	Pass criteria	Outcome
TC_WSN_01	SR_PR01_EIM_12_01	Electrodes of the EIM are made of washable electroconductive textiles.	WSN is designed using washable electroconductive textiles. Specific testing procedure needed (see 6.2.4)	Washing electroconductive textiles does not change EIM performance characteristics	Section 5.4

Functional requirements defined for EIM, LRM and LAM related to WSN are listed in Table 11.

Table 11. Laboratory-based functional system requirements test cases, in relation to EIM, LRM and LAM modules.

Test Case	Unique Requirement identifier	Description	Procedure	Pass criteria	Outcome
Electrical impedance module					
TC_WSN_02	SR_PR01_EIM_1_01	The EIM contains of a tetrapolar electrode where: the two outer electrodes are used for current injection, and the two inner electrodes for voltage measurement.	WSN is designed with four electrodes in parallel Each electrode can be connected to a different electrical connector with no interference.	the tetrapolar electrode system is available for accurate bioimpedance measurements	Pass
TC_WSN_03	SR_PR01_EIM_13_01	Electrodes of the EIM have adjustable circumference.	WSN is designed with Velcro adjustment to cover wide ranges of circumferences	Evaluation by users.	Pass Preliminary internal evaluation To be tested also with users during usability evaluation during Clinical study
TC_WSN_04	SR_PR01_EIM_15_01	The EIM is integrated into a biocompatible wearable with the LRM and the LAM	EIM electrodes are integrated into WSN straps, which also include specific solution for housing LRM sensor and LAM sensors	The EIM fits into the biocompatible wearable.	Pass
			Specific testing procedure needed:	Material is tested and	Not performed

			Biocompatibility is tested by certified laboratory	validated according to ISO 10993-1	yet Chosen materials are certified OEKO-TEX® STANDARD 100 class I and II
Light rheography module					
TC_WSN_05	SR_PR01_LRM_04_01	The LRM is integrated into a biocompatible and washable wearable with the EIP and the LAM.	WSN integrates EIM, LRM and LAM by design.	LRM sensor is integrated into WSN straps using a movable pocket. Straps also include EIM electrodes and specific solution for housing LAM sensors	Pass
			Specific testing procedure needed: Biocompatibility is tested by certified laboratory	Material is tested and validated according to ISO 10993-1	Not performed yet Chosen materials are certified OEKO-TEX® STANDARD 100 class I and II
TC_WSN_06	SR_PR01_LRM_11_01	Attachment: LRM modules must be attachable to lower extremity segments using comfortable Velcro straps.	WSN Strap including LRM sensor pocket can be adjusted and fixed with velcro	Fixation with velcro straps possible.	Pass
Limb activity module					
TC_WSN_07	SR_PR01_LAM_04_02	The LAM can accommodate up to 5 sensors per leg, with the minimum of one sensor per leg segment: 1) foot, 2) calf, 3) thigh.	WSN is designed with a minimum of 3 IMU Sensors housing.	3 housing for LAM sensors are placed in WSN straps: 1) foot, 2) calf, 3) thigh	Pass
TC_WSN_08	SR_PR01_LAM_12_01	The LAM is integrated into a biocompatible and washable wearable with the EIP and the LRM	LAM sensors are integrated into WSN straps using specific elastic band. Straps also include EIM electrodes and	the LAM fits into the washable and biocompatible wearable.	Pass

			specific solution for LRM sensor		
			Specific testing procedure needed: Biocompatibility is tested by certified laboratory	Material is tested and validated according to ISO 10993-1	Not performed yet Chosen materials are certified OEKO-TEX® STANDARD 100 class I and II

5.3. User requirements verification

Based on the above-mentioned test cases and the resulting outcomes, the verification of the identified user requirements for the electrical impedance module is performed by the same System requirements test cases, that stem from the User requirements. All user requirements for the textile wearable are listed below in Table 12, with listed corresponding test cases that verify each user requirement.

Table 12. Laboratory-based functional system requirements test cases, in relation to EIM, LRM and LAM modules.

User Requirement ID	User Requirement Description	Test Case ID's	Outcome
UR_PR01_EIM_03_01	To be biocompatible ensuring no adverse reaction during prolonged wear (ISO 10993, IEC 60601).	TC_WSN_04	Not verified yet
UR_PR01_EIM_04_01	Electrodes should have reliable contact with the skin and be reusable.	TC_WSN_03	Verified
UR_PR01_EIM_05_01	To permit easy wearing procedure.	TC_WSN_03 TC_WSN_04	Verified
UR_PR01_LRM_04_01	To permit easy wearing procedure.	TC_WSN_05 TC_WSN_06	Verified
UR_PR01_LAM_03_01	To be biocompatible and ensuring no adverse reaction during prolonged wear (ISO 10993, IEC 60601).	TC_WSN_08	Not verified yet
UR_PR01_LAM_04_01	To permit easy wearing procedure.	TC_WSN_08	Verified

5.4. Cleaning endurance testing

Testing for cleaning (TC_WSN_CL)

Both TC_WSN_01 is related to washability of the textile electrodes of the electrical impedance module (EIM). The selected materials used for textile electrodes can be washed multiple times, but this procedure aims to test their resistance to the suggested cleaning procedure, which includes washing and disinfection.

Cleaning procedures can be done in 2 ways:

- Amuchina Spray Disinfectant, a surgical medical device suitable for a bactericidal, fungicidal and virucidal action on textiles, can be used before the washing cycle. (Testing protocol 1)
- Cold wash and ozone disinfection. This procedure requires specific tools and the procedure involves an external laundry. (Testing protocol 2)

Materials for testing:

- Manufactured prototypes;
- Prepared testing protocols;
- Multimeter;
- Amuchina Spray Disinfectant (product link);
- Washing machine.

Two different electroconductive textiles are considered for the wearable sensor network (WSN) prototypes, the testing protocols are repeated for both (Table 13, Table 14).

Table 13. Testing protocol 1 (TC_WSN_CL_01): Cleaning procedure with Amuchina Spray Disinfectant.

Steps	Description	Procedure	Pass Criteria	Outcome
TC_WSN_CL_01_01	Collect textile electrodes' starting values	Use the multimeter to measure the electrical resistance of each electrode and collect them for reference. 1 lead on the snap and 1 on the electrode stripe.	Multimeter displays values $3\Omega < \text{Starting value} < 10\Omega$	Pass
TC_WSN_CL_01_02	Disinfect the wearable that includes EIM electrodes	Spray the disinfectant directly on the wearable until it is wet and leave the product to act for 15 minutes for bactericidal, fungicidal and virucidal action	-	N/A
TC_WSN_CL_01_03	Prepare the wearable that includes EIM electrodes for washing	Close the Velcro, make sure the textile electrodes are inside the wearable (no inside-out washing), place the wearable inside washing bags	-	N/A
TC_WSN_CL_01_04	Wash the wearable that includes EIM electrodes	Start the washing machine cycle at 40°C with mild detergent and no softener	-	N/A
TC_WSN_CL_01_05	Let the wearable dry	No tumble dryer, avoid direct sunlight on the electrodes	-	N/A
TC_WSN_CL_01_06	Collect textile electrodes' final values	Use multimeter to measure electrical resistance of each electrode and compare them to the previous measurement	For each electrode: $3\Omega < \text{Final value} < 10\Omega$	Pass

Table 14. Testing protocol 2 (TC_WSN_CL_02): Cleaning procedure with cold washing and ozone.

Steps	Description	Procedure	Pass Criteria	Outcome
TC_WSN_CL_02_01	Collect textile electrodes' starting values	Use multimeter to measure electrical resistance of each electrode and collect them for reference	Multimeter displays values $3\Omega < \text{Starting value} < 10\Omega$	Pass
TC_WSN_CL_02_02	Prepare the wearable for washing and drop off to the external laundry	Close the Velcro, make sure the textile electrodes are inside the wearable (no inside-out washing), place the wearable inside washing bags	-	N/A
TC_WSN_CL_02_03	Wash and disinfect the wearable that includes EIM electrodes	Specific laundry procedure: Soaking (40' 20°C) Pre-wash (5' 30°C) Wash (16' 40°C) Rinse in ozonated water (5' 20°C) Spin 7'	-	N/A
TC_WSN_CL_02_04	Let the wearable dry	No tumble dryer, avoid direct sunlight on the electrodes	-	N/A
TC_WSN_CL_02_05	Measure textile electrodes' final values	Use the multimeter to measure the electrical resistance of each electrode and compare them to the previous measurement	For each electrode: $3\Omega < \text{Final value} < 10\Omega$	Pass

6. Discussion and conclusion

The hardware testing of electrical impedance module (EIM), light rheography module (LRM) and limb activity module (LAM), covering both the measurement performance and device's general functionality, showed that all devices are sufficiently accurate, perform as expected and cover all user and system requirements defined in D2.3². The developed experimental graphical user interfaces (GUIs) allowed the testing and demonstration of the systems' operation, and will facilitate integration in the project scope. Functional tests related to the modules' software development kits (SDKs) demonstrated that the developed SDKs provide the required functionality to control the measurement devices.

The EIP system is suitable for measuring lower limb bioimpedance, the LRM system is suitable for measuring lower limb light reflection rheography and the LAM system is suitable for estimating lower limb orientation, as well as measuring activity, photoplethysmography, body temperature and ambient temperature. The functional testing of the textile wearable of the ThrombUS+ wearable sensor network showed that the design is suitable for integrating all systems developed in WP3 and WP4 effectively and ergonomically. The cleaning procedure tests of wearable showed that the prototype sustained its mechanical and electrical properties after the cleaning procedures.

² Marozas V, Kaldoudi E, Prinz T, Lukoševičius A, Jurkonis R, Eitminavičius R, Didaskalou S, Vehkaoja A, Ahola R, Slabov A, Jegelevičius D, Balling S, Moutafidou A, Daukantas S, Rapalis A. Technical and functional requirements, Deliverable 2.3, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 31 October 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13897671>.